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1. Executive summary

This document presents deliverable D1.4 “Report on the methodological framework at landscape scale” which presents the results of the first task of workpackage 4 “Definition of the methodology for ecosystem services assessment at landscape scale” of the UNDERTREES project. It discusses the importance of ecosystem services for natural resource management and conservation as well as the concept of ecosystem services provision, particularly those related with agroforestry systems. Highlighted is the need for holistic approaches in managing natural resources and for frameworks that identify and quantify the benefits of agroforestry systems in the form of ecosystem services.

Various approaches and tools for assessing ecosystem services at the landscape scale are mentioned, including the use of models such as InVEST and others and, finally, models for several ecosystem services are suggested as well as other alternative methodological approaches, such as the European Integrated Natural Capital Accounting (INCA), for cases where data requirements for InVEST models are difficult to fulfil.

The methodology for assessing ecosystem services at the landscape scale using InVEST tools and models is briefly described. The suggested software suite includes a collection of tools that help to assess ecosystem services by means of models and maps and to value those ecosystem services. The models are based on production functions that describe the relationships between changes in ecosystem structure and function and the resulting impacts on the flow and value of ecosystem services across a given landscape. The models are particularly suited for landscape-scale assessments in the UNDERTREES project for several reasons, including their flexibility and adaptability to different contexts and scales, their ability to estimate multiple ecosystem services and their user-friendly interface.

This report also describes the specific ecosystem services that can be assessed with the InVEST package in agroforestry systems under the UNDERTREES interest and define the set of models and tools that could help to cover the modelling needs regarding: carbon storage, water quality and quantity, crop production, biodiversity and cultural services.

2. Introduction and key concepts

2.1. Ecosystem services

The benefits that natural systems provide to humans are known as ecosystem services. These benefits are classified into four categories: provisioning services (e.g., food, water, and fiber), regulating services (e.g., climate regulation, flood control, and pest control), supporting services (e.g., nutrient cycling, soil formation, and primary production), and cultural services (e.g., recreation, aesthetic enjoyment, and spiritual experiences). Ecosystem services are essential for human well-being and support economic, social, and cultural activities. The concept of ecosystem services has gained significant attention in recent years, but it has been recognized for centuries by philosophers, economists, and ecologists (Costanza et al., 1997; Daily, 1997). However, it was only in the last few decades that the concept gained a broader audience and was widely adopted by policymakers, practitioners, and researchers (Balvanera et al., 2014).

Studying ecosystem services has important implications for natural resource management and conservation. It highlights the need for a more holistic approach to managing natural resources, one that recognizes the interdependence of human well-being and ecosystem health. It also provides a

framework for identifying and quantifying the benefits of conservation and restoration activities and for prioritizing management actions that will have the greatest positive impact on human well-being.

The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA) report, published in 2005, is one of the most influential reports on ecosystem services (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). The MEA was a comprehensive assessment of the world's ecosystems and their contributions to human well-being. It defined ecosystem services as "the benefits people obtain from ecosystems" and provided a framework for categorizing and assessing ecosystem services. It identified the main drivers of ecosystem change and their implications for human well-being. Since the publication of the MEA, there has been a growing body of research that seeks to understand the relationships between ecosystems and the delivery of ecosystem services. This includes studies that explore the links between biodiversity and ecosystem services (Maes et al., 2016), the impacts of land use change on ecosystem services (De Groot et al., 2010), and the trade-offs between different ecosystem services (Raudsepp-Hearne, 2010). There is also a growing recognition of the importance of ecosystem services in promoting sustainable development and addressing global challenges such as climate change, food security, and biodiversity loss.

To categorize and systematize the growing number of ecosystem services identified, the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) was developed. The CICES is a framework for the consistent and comprehensive classification of ecosystem services developed by the Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services (MAES) initiative of the European Commission. The use of a standardized classification system like CICES V5.1 (Haines-Young and Potschin, 2019) allows for easier comparison and integration of ecosystem service assessments across different regions and ecosystems. It also helps to ensure that ecosystem services are consistently and comprehensively identified, assessed, and managed.

The latest version 5.1 of CICES (Figure 1) is based on a hierarchical structure that includes five levels of classification, each with increasing degree of detail and specificity. The five levels are:

Level 1: Divisions – This level divides ecosystem services into broad categories based on the benefit they provide, such as provisioning, regulating, and cultural services.

Level 2: Groups – This level groups ecosystem services based on the type of benefit they provide within each division, such as food production for provisioning services.

Level 3: Classes – This level further subdivides each group into specific classes of ecosystem services, such as crop production for food provisioning services.

Level 4: Types – This level provides further detail on each class, such as different types of crops that provide food provisioning services.

Level 5: Instances – This level includes specific examples of each type, such as specific varieties of crops that provide food provisioning services.

Figure 1. Hierarchical structure of CICES, illustrated with reference to a provisioning service (cultivated plants- cereals) (Source: MEA, 2005).

In the following a simplified list of the CICES V5.1 is included, along with examples of some of the main ecosystem services included in each category:

Level 1:

Provisioning Services:

- Food (e.g. crops, livestock, fish)
- Water (e.g. freshwater, marine, groundwater)
- Raw materials (e.g. timber, fibre, fuel)
- Medicinal resources (e.g. plants, animals)
- Ornamental resources (e.g. flowers, plants)

Regulating and Maintenance Services:

- Climate regulation (e.g. carbon sequestration, air quality)
- Water regulation (e.g. flood control, erosion prevention)
- Soil formation and protection (e.g. nutrient cycling, soil structure)
- Pollination and seed dispersal (e.g. bees, birds)
- Pest regulation (e.g. natural predators, disease control)

Cultural Services:

- Aesthetic and cultural value (e.g. recreation, tourism)
- Spiritual and religious value (e.g. sacred sites, cultural heritage)
- Educational and scientific value (e.g. research, learning)

Supporting Services:

- Biodiversity maintenance (e.g. habitat provision, genetic diversity)
- Nutrient cycling (e.g. nitrogen fixation, nutrient retention)
- Primary production (e.g. photosynthesis, energy flow)

Level 2:

- Crop production (provisioning)
- Surface and groundwater supply (provisioning)
- Timber and non-timber forest products (provisioning)
- Carbon sequestration and storage (regulating and maintenance)
- Water flow regulation (regulating and maintenance)
- Soil conservation and fertility (regulating and maintenance)
- Pollination (regulating and maintenance)
- Natural hazard regulation (regulating and maintenance)
- Biological control (regulating and maintenance)
- Cultural and amenity services (cultural)
- Knowledge systems (cultural)
- Landscape values (cultural)
- Genetic resources (supporting)
- Ecosystem diversity (supporting)
- Soil formation (supporting)
- Nutrient cycling (supporting)
- Primary production (supporting)

Level 3 provides further detail and examples for each ecosystem service class.

2.2. Ecosystem services in agroforestry systems

Agroforestry systems are land use practices that combine woody vegetation (trees or shrubs) with crop and/or livestock systems to benefit from the resulting ecological and economic interactions (Burgess and Rosati, 2018), and can provide a wide range of ecosystem services. Those systems have been found to provide multiple and diverse benefits, compared to other land uses, due to the integration of trees, crops, and livestock. For example, studies have shown that agroforestry systems can provide higher levels of biodiversity, soil conservation, carbon sequestration, and water regulation compared to monoculture systems. The diversity of tree species, crops, and livestock in agroforestry systems also allows for a more resilient and adaptive system, better able to withstand environmental stressors such as climate change. Another important aspect is that agroforestry systems can provide economic benefits through the production of varied goods, such as timber, fruits and nuts, as well as non-timber forest products, such as medicinal plants and honey. In this sense, agroforestry can be considered as a promising approach for sustainable land use management that integrates environmental, social, and economic aspects. These are just a few examples of the many ecosystem services that agroforestry systems can provide (Figure 2).

It is important to note that the specific ecosystem services provided by agroforestry systems will depend on the characteristics of the system, its management practices and the local context; so that different authors may consider a diversity of ecosystem services to be important when evaluating agroforestry systems (Palacios and Bokelmann, 2017).

In general, some of the most frequently cited ecosystem services associated with agroforestry systems include:

- Water regulation and purification
- Biodiversity conservation
- Provision of timber, non-timber products, and fuelwood
- Carbon sequestration, climate and microclimate regulation
- Soil conservation, erosion control and fertility improvement
- Pest and disease control
- Pollination services

To resume, the distinctive characteristics of agroforestry systems in relation to several of these ecosystem services are:

- **Biodiversity:** Agroforestry systems can enhance biodiversity, providing habitats for a range of species, including pollinators, birds, and mammals. Agroforestry systems usually present higher levels of biodiversity compared to monoculture agricultural systems, as they incorporate trees, crops, and/or livestock. This leads to greater provision of ecosystem services related to biodiversity, such as habitat provision for wildlife and pollinators. Agroforestry systems can also support the conservation of threatened species and their habitats (Schroth and Sinclair., 2004; Jose, 2009).
- **Pollination and pest regulation:** Agroforestry systems can enhance pollination and pest regulation services through the presence of trees and shrubs that provide habitat and food for pollinators and natural enemies of pests. This can lead to improved crop yields and reduced pesticide use (Tscharrntke et al., 2011; Jose, 2009).

Figure 2. Agroforestry system types and ecosystem services. Source: Palacios and Bokelmann (2017).

- *Soil conservation, fertility and erosion control:* Erosion is a significant issue in many agricultural systems, and it can lead to excessive soil loss, reduced productivity, and environmental degradation. Agroforestry systems promote soil conservation and fertility by reducing soil erosion and improving soil structure. Trees and shrubs in agroforestry systems can help prevent excessive soil loss and improve soil quality, which in turn can improve water quality. In comparison to other agricultural systems, agroforestry has been shown to be effective in reducing erosion rates, typically presenting greater amount of vegetation cover compared to monoculture systems, which can help to reduce erosion rates. Moreover, the roots of the trees and shrubs can penetrate deeper into the soil, helping to stabilize it and reduce erosion rates (Rao et al., 2000). Another factor that contributes to the erosion control benefits of agroforestry is the presence of mulch, which helps to reduce erosion rates by increasing infiltration and reducing runoff (Huang et al. 2022.) also helping to improve soil fertility (Schroth and Sinclair, 2004). Additionally, the canopy of trees and shrubs in agroforestry systems can help to intercept rainfall, reducing the velocity of raindrops and minimizing their impact on the soil surface (Schoeneberger et al., 2004). All this leads to greater provision of other ecosystem services related to soil conservation, such as nutrient cycling and water filtration (Garrity et al., 2010).
- *Climate change mitigation and adaptation:* Agroforestry systems can mitigate and adapt to climate change by sequestering carbon in trees and soil, reducing greenhouse gas emissions from livestock and increasing resilience to extreme weather events (Nair et al., 2010, Kumar et al. 2011; Franzel et al., 2014). Significant amounts of carbon are sequestered, both in aboveground biomass and soil organic matter, that helps to mitigate climate change and provide co-benefits such as improved soil fertility and water holding capacity. In terms of the microclimate, trees in agroforestry systems can provide shade, reducing heat stress and increasing humidity, which can benefit both crops and livestock (Nair, 2014).
- *Livelihoods and food security:* Agroforestry systems can improve livelihoods and food security by providing diverse sources of income and food from trees, livestock, and crops grown under the tree canopy (Garrity et al., 2010).
- *Provision of food, timber and non-timber forest products:* Agroforestry systems can provide timber and non-timber products such as fruits, nuts, and medicinal plants, that constitute food for human consumption and animal feed. Moreover, the combination of trees with crops and/or livestock can enhance the productivity and sustainability of food production (Lin, 2011).
- *Water regulation and conservation:* Trees and shrubs in agroforestry systems can regulate water flow, reducing flooding and, sometimes, increasing water availability during dry periods. Water conservation is also improved by reducing water runoff and increasing water infiltration into the soil (Yuniti et al., 2022), which contribute to reduce the risk of flooding and enhance water availability for crops and livestock. Agroforestry systems can also contribute to groundwater recharge and reduce water stress in drylands (Lin et al., 2015).

2.3. Assessment of ecosystem services

One of the main challenges in the study of ecosystem services is to develop effective methods for assessing and, eventually, valuing them. This requires taking into account the complex interactions between ecosystems and human well-being while addressing issues such as spatial and temporal scales, uncertainty and equity. The assessment of ecosystem services has become increasingly important in

policy and management decisions, as it provides a framework for understanding the trade-offs and synergies among different ecosystem services and for informing decisions that affect the provision of these services (Tallis et al., 2018). The assessment of ecosystem services at the landscape scale is crucial, for example, to understand the spatial and temporal dynamics of the services themselves (Burkhard et al., 2012).

As a complex and broad issue, assessing ecosystem services should involve a combination of scientific, economic, and social approaches and the use of spatial analysis tools (Tallis et al., 2018). On the scientific side, ecological data is needed that include information on the physical and biological characteristics of ecosystems, such as land cover, soil type, biodiversity or hydrology. Social data can include information on the human activities and interests related to ecosystems, such as land use, cultural practices or economic activities. Spatial analysis tools are frequently used to map and quantify ecosystem services and to identify the trade-offs and synergies between different services and stakeholders.

There exist a variety of methodologies and tools available to accomplish these assessments, that range from qualitative to quantitative approaches. These methodologies typically involve the following steps:

- The first step is to identify the ecosystem types present, such as forests, wetlands, grasslands, or agricultural lands. This can be done, for example, using remote sensing imagery or field surveys.
- Once the ecosystem types are identified, the next step is to define the ecosystem services provided by each type. This can be done by consulting with experts or by using existing literature.
- The next step involves quantification of the ecosystem services provided by each ecosystem type. This can be done using a combination of field surveys, remote sensing, modelling, or accessing to knowledge data bases. For example, the carbon sequestration potential of a forest can be estimated using remote sensing and modelling.
- Furthermore, the value of ecosystem services provided by each ecosystem type can be assessed. A variety of methods can be used, such as market or non-market valuation. For example, the market value of timber harvested from a forest can be used to estimate the economic value of the forest ecosystem service, while the non-market value of recreational activities can be estimated using surveys.
- The final step is to synthesize the results of the ecosystem services assessment and present them in a useful format for decision-makers. This can involve creating maps, graphs and tables that illustrate the ecosystem services provided by each ecosystem type and their value.

Nevertheless, the assessment of ecosystem services faces several challenges and limitations, including the lack of standardized methods and data, the difficulty in quantifying certain services and the trade-offs between different services and stakeholders. Additionally, ecosystem services are often undervalued in economic terms, leading to underinvestment in their conservation and management (Costanza et al, 1997). In an effort to address these challenges, various initiatives have been implemented and global frameworks have been established to evaluate and quantify the value of ecosystem services, such as the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, the Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity or the Natural Capital Project. These initiatives aim to promote the integration of ecosystem services into decision-making processes and to enhance the understanding of the importance of ecosystems for human well-being, and are summarized below for their relevance.

- The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA) (Figure 3) is a global assessment of the consequences of ecosystem change for human well-being that was conducted between 2001 and 2005 (MEA, 2005). The MEA aimed to assess the status and trends of ecosystem services, the

drivers of change in ecosystems and the options for managing ecosystems sustainably. It identified four categories of ecosystem services: provisioning, regulating, supporting and cultural services. The MEA also provided a framework for assessing the value of ecosystem services in economic and non-economic terms.

- The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity (TEEB) (Figure 4) is a global initiative that focuses on the economics of ecosystems and biodiversity (Braat and de Groot, 2012). The TEEB aims to provide decision-makers with tools and information to support the sustainable management of ecosystems and the conservation of biodiversity and uses economic valuation methods to assess the value of ecosystem services and to make the case for investing in ecosystem conservation and restoration.

Figure 3. Millennium Ecosystem Assessment overview diagram (MEA, 2005).

Figure 4. The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity overview diagram (Braat and de Groot, 2012)

- The Natural Capital Project (Figure 5) (<https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/>) is a partnership between several organizations, including Stanford University and The Nature Conservancy, that aims to mainstream the consideration of natural capital in decision-making (Natural Capital Project, 2021). The Natural Capital Project develops tools and approaches for integrating ecosystem services into decision-making processes (NatCap process), such as the InVEST (Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs) tool. InVEST is a software suite that allows users to map and quantify ecosystem services and to evaluate the trade-offs between different services and stakeholders.

Figure 5. The NatCap process
(https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/sites/default/files/natcap_process.jpg).

Apart from the abovementioned, a variety of methodologies, techniques and tools have been developed to assess and value ecosystem services. Those involve ecological models, economic valuation, participatory approaches, or spatial analysis tools. However, there is still a need for further research to improve the accuracy and reliability of ecosystem services assessment and valuation, and to better integrate ecosystem services into policy and decision-making.

Ecological models are used to understand the relationships between different components of the agroforestry system and their impacts on ecosystem services. For example, models can be used to predict the impact of agroforestry practices on soil erosion, nutrient cycling, or water quality. Some examples of ecological models used in agroforestry systems include the Agroforestry System Simulator (AFSYS), the Soil Water Atmosphere Plant (SWAP) model, and the Agroforestry Productivity Simulator (APSIM).

Economic valuation is used to put a monetary value on the ecosystem services provided by agroforestry systems. This can help to demonstrate the economic benefits of agroforestry and make the case for its adoption. Different methods of economic valuation include the travel cost method, the contingent valuation method, and the hedonic pricing method.

Participatory approaches involve engaging with stakeholders, such as farmers and local communities, in the mapping and modelling process. This can help to ensure that the values and needs of local people are taken into account and that the mapping and modelling process is transparent and inclusive. Participatory approaches include techniques such as participatory mapping, focus group discussions or stakeholder workshops.

In addition to these approaches, spatial analysis can also be performed when mapping and modelling ecosystem services in agroforestry systems. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) technologies can be used to analyse spatial data and create maps of ecosystem services and land use patterns. This can help

to identify areas of high and low ecosystem service provision, and inform decision-making about land use and management.

2.4. Ecosystem services modelling and mapping

Models are widely utilized among the various tools and approaches to evaluate ecosystem services, being particularly noteworthy as assessment resources that aid in comprehending the advantages that ecosystems offer to humans and can facilitate more sustainable decisions regarding, for example, changes in land use. There are several reasons why it may be necessary to model ecosystem services; some of those key reasons include (Braat and de Groot, 2012):

- Understanding trade-offs: Modelling ecosystem services can help understand the trade-offs between different services. For example, protecting a forest may provide benefits such as carbon sequestration, but it may also limit agricultural opportunities. Modelling can help identify the costs and benefits of different land use decisions.
- Supporting decision-making: Modelling can also support decision-making by providing information on the potential impacts of different management or policy scenarios. This can help decision-makers make informed choices that maximize benefits and minimize negative impacts.
- Improving communication: Modelling ecosystem services can improve communication between different stakeholders, such as scientists, policymakers, and land managers. By using a common language and set of tools, stakeholders can better understand the trade-offs and benefits of different land use decisions.
- Identifying data gaps: Modelling can also help identify data gaps and research needs. For example, if a model indicates that there is uncertainty around the provision of a particular ecosystem service, this may signal a need for additional research to improve our understanding of the underlying processes.

Land managers often face a challenge when it comes to choosing an appropriate ecosystem model from the ever-increasing number of them for quantifying and mapping the services of a particular area. Therefore, there is a need for practical frameworks to aid in selecting reliable models suitable for specific knowledge levels, geographies and scales of particular cases. These models should ideally be able to evaluate the site's capacity to deliver specific services, the demand for ecosystem services and the actual supply. As all these three aspects of ecosystem service provision are seldom found in one model, a collection of them is usually required that complement each other regarding drivers, data, scale and knowledge.

Kienast and Helfenstein (2016) compiled a classification of ecosystem services models as:

- Process based models
- Empirical models
- Tiered approaches
- Indicator-based assessments
- Landscape models

Process-based models use a detailed understanding of the biophysical and ecological processes that underlie the provision of ecosystem services. They require high-quality data and a good understanding

of ecosystem dynamics, but can provide a very accurate assessment of the provision of ecosystem services.

Empirical models use statistical relationships to predict the provision of ecosystem services based on past observations of service provision and the environmental factors that affect it. Empirical models are less data-intensive than process-based models, but may not capture well the complexity of ecosystem processes.

Tiered approaches use a combination of process-based and empirical models to assess ecosystem services provision. They often involve a series of simplified models at different spatial and temporal scales, with more complex models used only in areas where there is a higher level of data availability.

Indicator-based assessments sets of existing or developed indicators to assess the provision of ecosystem services. These indicators are often based on proxies for ecosystem function or structure, and can be used to compare the provision of different ecosystem services.

Landscape models use spatially explicit data on land use, ecosystem function and environmental conditions to simulate the provision of ecosystem services across a landscape. They can be used to identify areas where the provision of ecosystem services is likely to be high or low, and to assess the impact of different land use scenarios on the provision of ecosystem services.

Table 1 shows a list of different models and their applications, classified according to the model types mentioned above, which is only a selection of commonly used models and their main uses.

Despite the model selection, most of the ecosystem functions and processes that lead to the generation of ecosystem services exhibit significant temporal and spatial variation and are dependent on scale. Drivers of change that impact and modify these functions and processes exhibit spatial variability including, for example, land use patterns, land fragmentation, and intensification of agriculture. Consequently, it is important to provide ecosystem service maps that describe and assess the production of ecosystem services based on ecosystem processes such as land-use patterns, climate or environmental variation, in general. On the other hand, mapping ecosystem services as supply and demand can be useful for decision-making processes such as land use planning, environmental impact assessment or landscape management.

Furthermore, the supply of ecosystem services is a multifaceted process, often marked by interrelationships between different services and trade-offs, so that, for example, bundles and synergies between different ecosystem services and between ecosystem services and biodiversity are common, and the production of one service may result in a reduction or increase in another. A comprehensive understanding of this complex system also requires mapping of ecosystem services and knowledge of their spatial distribution (Maes et al., 2013).

Table 1. Examples of models and their main applications classified according to the typology suggested in Kienast and Helfenstein (2016).

Model Type	Examples	Applications
Process-based	CENTURY (Parton et al., 1987) Biome-BGC (Running and Hunt, 1993) InVEST (Tallis and Polasky, 2009) MODIS (Didan et al., 2015)	Land use planning, policy analysis, decision support. Assessment of ecosystem services supply, identifying management practices to improve service provision
Empirical	GLOBIO, RIOS, LUCAS, ARIES, REGARDS, MIMES. Statistical models developed using techniques as Random Forest (Breiman, 2001), Maximum Entropy (Phillips et al., 2006), Boosted Regression Trees (Friedman, 2001), Multiple Linear Regression (Legendre and Legendre, 1998).	Policy analysis, ecosystem service valuation. Evaluation of ecosystem services supply and demand, assessing trade-offs and synergies
Tiered	TESSA (Braat and de Groot, 2012) RIOS CICES (Haines-Young and Potschin, 2018)	Decision support, land use planning. Assessment of ecosystem services supply and demand, identification of management practices to improve service provision
Indicator-based	DPSIR (European Environment Agency, 1999) Pressure-State-Response (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, 1993)	Ecosystem service valuation, policy analysis. Assessment of ecosystem services supply and demand, integrating ecosystem services into policy and decision making
Landscape	STEPPS (Schröter et al., 2014) InVEST (Tallis and Polasky, 2009) LUCI (Bryan et al., 2011) LANDIS-II (Scheller et al., 2007) LFA (Tongway and Hindley, 2004) BenMAP (Sacks et al., 2018)	Landscape management, conservation planning. Assessment of ecosystem services supply and demand, identifying management practices to improve service provision at a landscape scale

2.5. Scale of analysis. Assessment at landscape scale

One of the challenges in assessing ecosystem services is to account for the different scales at which services are provided and valued. Ecosystem services can be assessed at multiple scales, from local to landscape to global, depending on the context and objectives of the assessment. At the local or landscape scale, the focus usually relies on understanding the services provided by specific land parcels, ecosystems or landscapes and their importance for local communities and economies. At the global scale, the focus is on understanding the contribution of ecosystems to the global economy and the impacts of global drivers of change, such as climate change and land use change, on ecosystem services (Braat and de Groot, 2012).

There are several commonly used approaches to model ecosystem services at landscape scale, including:

- **Habitat suitability modelling:** This approach uses species distribution models and environmental data to assess the potential habitat suitability of a landscape for different species. It can be used

to identify areas that are important for biodiversity conservation and to evaluate the impacts of different land use scenarios on wildlife habitat.

- Land use/land cover change modelling: This approach uses remote sensing data and GIS tools to model the changes in land use and land cover over time. It can be used to evaluate the impacts of land use change on ecosystem services, such as carbon sequestration and water regulation.
- Ecological process modelling: This approach uses mechanistic models to simulate the ecological processes that support ecosystem services, such as nutrient cycling and pollination. It can be used to evaluate the impacts of different land use scenarios on these processes and to identify critical thresholds and tipping points.
- Multi-criteria decision analysis: This approach uses a combination of environmental, social, and economic criteria to evaluate the trade-offs and synergies between different land use scenarios. It can be used to support decision-making and to identify management strategies that optimize ecosystem services.
- Ecosystem service mapping: This approach involves mapping the spatial distribution of ecosystem services in a landscape using GIS tools and spatial models. It can be used to identify priority areas for conservation and to evaluate the impacts of different land use scenarios on ecosystem services.

These modelling approaches can be used alone or in combination to provide a comprehensive assessment of ecosystem services at the landscape scale. The choice of approach depends on the research question, the availability of data, and the spatial and temporal scale of the study.

3. Methodology for ES assessment at landscape scale: InvVEST tools and models

In order to fulfil the demands of Task 4.1 outlined in the UNDERTREES project regarding the establishment of a framework for assessing ecosystem services at the landscape level, this report will delve into suggested landscape modelling techniques and mapping tools. Furthermore, this report will take into account the insights and specific concerns discussed in sections 1.3 to 1.5 of the report.

There are several methodologies and tools available for assessing ecosystem services at the landscape scale, such as the Landscape Function Analysis (LFA) or the Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Trade-offs (InVEST). These tools provide frameworks for assessing some biophysical and socio-economic aspects of ecosystem services and for integrating this information into decision-making processes.

The InVEST (Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs) software suite is a collection of tools designed to model and map the provision and value of ecosystem services. It is a widely used open-source tool that has been developed by researchers at the Natural Capital Project in collaboration with various partners. The software suite provides a range of models that can be used to evaluate different ecosystem services, including water regulation, carbon storage, and habitat quality (Figure 6).

From a technical point of view, the main characteristics of InVEST models are:

- InVEST utilizes maps both as inputs and outputs, providing spatially-explicit results that can be expressed in biophysical terms (e.g. carbon sequestration in tons) or economic terms (e.g. the net present value of carbon sequestration). The flexibility of the tool allows users to choose the spatial resolution of their analysis, from local to global scales.
- Models are based on production functions that describe the relationship between changes in ecosystem structure and function and the resulting impacts on the flow and value of ecosystem services across a given landscape. These models account for both the supply of ecosystem services (e.g., living habitats that serve as buffers against storms) and the location and activities of beneficiaries of these services (e.g. people and infrastructure potentially impacted by coastal storms).
- InVEST is distributed as a standalone application that does not require a GIS software. However, mapping software such as QGIS or ArcGIS is needed to view the results. While InVEST does not require knowledge of Python programming, though it does require basic to intermediate skills in GIS software.
- Is a modular tool, allowing users to select and model only the ecosystem services that are of interest to them. This flexibility enables users to tailor their analyses to their specific needs and objectives.

Additionally, InVEST provides a set of helper tools that simplify some of the common operations and technical issues that are needed when running models, such as the watersheds delineation, calculation of flow directions or data visualization tasks.

Figure 5. Schematic view of InVEST models and linkages. Source: <https://unstats.un.org/unsd/envaccounting/seeaRev/meeting2013/EG13-2-InVEST.pdf>.

3.1. Suitability of InVEST models for UNDERTREES

InVEST is particularly suited for landscape-scale assessments in the UNDERTREES project for several reasons:

- InVEST provides a suite of models that can estimate the multiple ecosystem services that a landscape can provide. These models are designed to be used together, allowing users to examine the interactions and trade-offs among different ecosystem services in a given landscape. This approach aligns with the landscape-scale approach, which recognizes that ecosystems are complex and interconnected systems that operate at multiple spatial and temporal scales.
- In addition, models are designed to be flexible and adaptable to different contexts and scales. It can be used to assess ecosystem services in a variety of landscapes, including agricultural areas, forests, wetlands or coastal zones. Furthermore, InVEST can be customized to reflect the specific characteristics of a study area, such as its topography, climate, and land use. This adaptability allows users to tailor the tool to their specific needs and objectives.

- Another advantage of this set of models is its user-friendly interface, which allows users with little to no technical expertise to run the models and interpret the results. The interface is designed to be intuitive and accessible, with detailed documentation and tutorials to guide users through the process. This makes InVEST an effective tool for engaging with stakeholders and decision-makers at different levels, from local communities to regional or national governments.

3.2. UNDERTREES’ needs and available InVEST models

The set of ecosystem services that can be assessed with the InVEST package are:

- Carbon
- Coastal Blue Carbon
- Coastal Vulnerability
- Crop Pollination
- Crop Production
- Habitat Quality
- Habitat Risk Assessment
- Offshore Wind Energy
- Recreation
- Reservoir Hydropower Production (Water Yield)
- Scenic Quality
- Seasonal Water Yield
- Sediment Retention
- Urban Cooling
- Urban Flood Risk Mitigation
- Urban Stormwater Retention
- Water Purification
- Wave Energy

It is considered that, in order to address the specific needs of the UNDERTREES project, the models selected from the precedent list could be adequate to assess and simulate ecosystem services related to carbon storage and sequestration, timber, food and fibre production, soil erosion, water balance and quality, flood and nutrient regulation, and biodiversity services such as pollination. Moreover, cultural services like recreational opportunities and aesthetic value can also be assessed. Additional assessment of other ecosystem services like pest and disease control will be achieved by using other indicators or models.

With these considerations, InVEST set of models and tools could help to cover the modelling needs of the UNDERTREES project regarding the following subjects:

- Carbon storage and sequestration: The amount of carbon stored in different types of vegetation, soil, and land use types can be estimated. This information can be used to identify opportunities for carbon sequestration and to evaluate the potential impacts of land use changes on carbon storage.
- Water quality and quantity: Models allow to estimate the impacts of land use changes on water quality and quantity. For example, the software can evaluate the effects of changes in land use on sedimentation, nutrient loading, and water availability.

- Crop production: Estimate crop yield and nutrient value for a fixed set of crops, derived from user-supplied land cover information. This information can be used to evaluate the economic value of crop yield and to identify sustainable management practices.
- Biodiversity services (Habitat quality): Models can assess the quality and suitability of habitats for various species. By considering factors such as vegetation structure, patch size, and connectivity, the models can help identify areas that are crucial for biodiversity conservation and inform habitat management strategies.
- Biodiversity services (Pollination): Models can estimate the value of pollination services provided by ecosystems. By considering factors like floral resources and proximity to pollinator habitats, the models can help assess the potential benefits of preserving or restoring habitats that support pollinators, thus aiding in the sustainability of agricultural and natural systems.
- Cultural services: Cultural ecosystem services, such as recreational opportunities and aesthetic values, can also be evaluated. By considering factors like accessibility, landscape beauty, and visitor preferences, the models can provide insights into the potential benefits and values associated with different landscapes and recreational activities.

4. UNDERTREES ecosystem service modelling: description, data needs and model outputs

4.1. Carbon Storage and Sequestration

Terrestrial ecosystems play a crucial role in mitigating carbon dioxide-driven climate change as they store a significant amount of carbon, surpassing that of the atmosphere. InVEST’s Carbon Storage and Sequestration model (Figure 6) utilizes land use maps and quantifies carbon stocks across four pools (aboveground biomass, belowground biomass, soil, and dead organic matter) to estimate the current carbon storage and the potential carbon sequestration rate over time in a given landscape. Additionally, the model allows for the incorporation of market or social values, annual change rates, and discount rates to assess the societal value of this ecosystem service. However, it’s important to note that the model has limitations, including an oversimplified representation of the carbon cycle, an assumption of linear carbon sequestration changes, and potential inaccuracies in discounting rates.

The main characteristics of carbon modelling in InVEST are:

- Carbon stock is calculated as a function of land use/land cover
- Storage indicates the mass of carbon in an ecosystem at any given point in time.
- Sequestration indicates the change in carbon storage in an ecosystem over time.
- Valuation is applied to sequestration

Please refer to the guide available in <http://releases.naturalcapitalproject.org/invest-userguide/latest/en/carbonstorage.html> for detailed information on the model characteristics and methodologies.

Figure 6. Schematic view of the carbon storage and sequestration model. Source: Maanan et al. (2019).

4.2. Water quality and quantity

Nutrient Delivery Ratio (NDR) (water purification), Sediment Delivery Ratio (SDR) and Seasonal Water Yield are the models implemented in InVEST package to assess water quality-related or water quantity-related ecosystem services at landscape scale.

4.2.1. Water purification: Nutrient Delivery Ratio (NDR) index, data needs and model outputs

The Nutrient Delivery Ratio (NDR) offered by the InVEST models (Figures 7) seeks to evaluate and assess the potential for nutrient pollution, mainly nitrogen and phosphorus, in aquatic systems through analysing the movement and delivery of these nutrients from lands to water bodies. The NDR carefully considers components such as soil characteristics, hydrology, topography, and land use when simulating the means of transporting and delivering these nutrients from landscapes to rivers, streams, and reservoirs.

Additionally, the model is designed to explore the spatial patterns of nutrient sources, pathways and sinks; thereby recognizing areas likely to be impacted by nutrient runoff. It determines the exact delivery ratio, offering information for understanding and checking nutrient contamination, eutrophication incidents and related impacts on aquatic environments.

Figure 7. Schematic view of the Nutrient Delivery Ratio (NDR) model. See <http://releases.naturalcapitalproject.org/invest-userguide/latest/en/ndr.html> for additional explanations and image source.

Within UNDERTREES, NDR can be applied to inspect alternative agroforestry management practices and determine the locations suitable for effective interventions designed to reduce the flow of nutrients into nearby water bodies. As a result, this provides salient insights for decision-making related to environmental conservation activities, farming and managing water resources with a primary goal of lessening nutrient pollution and preserving healthy aquatic ecosystems.

Please refer to the guide available in <http://releases.naturalcapitalproject.org/invest-userguide/latest/en/ndr.html> for detailed information on the model characteristics and methodologies, including models data needs and outputs.

4.2.2. Sediment Delivery Ratio (SDR) index, data needs and model outputs

The Sediment Delivery Ratio (SDR) model (Figure 8) is a spatially-explicit tool used to model soil erosion and sediment transport and deposition phenomena. It allows the spatially-explicit representation of the annual average soil loss and then computes the sediment delivery ratio which is the part of the soil loss that actually reaches the hydrographic network. The SDR model is useful to describe the hydrological linkage between sediment sources and destinations, among which are hydrographic network components. The SDR model is scientifically based on the theory of hydrological connectivity, which requires a small number of input layers and provides ease of implementation.

The SDR model is a useful tool for predicting the impacts related to land use changes. The results of the elaboration are precisely related to changes in land use, in order to highlight the domains in which spatial planning can act on the regional scale. The difficulty in finding detailed and spatialized data related to each of the factors that contribute to soil erosion has led to the increasing usage of models such as the SDR InVEST module, which is both simple and scientifically credible.

Data needs for running the SDR model include a digital elevation model (DEM), soil texture, land use, and rainfall data. The first result obtained from the implementation of the SDR module is a map of the spatial distribution within the regional territory of the annual soil loss gradient (t/ha). This map shows the different areas where soil erosion is more intense, allowing for the identification of priority areas for intervention. By using the SDR model, it is possible to estimate the proportion of soil eroded from a landscape that actually reaches a river or stream, where it can cause sedimentation and other problems. This information is useful for identifying areas where sedimentation is likely to occur and developing strategies to mitigate the impacts of soil erosion.

Figure 8. Schematic view of the Sediment Delivery Ratio (NDR) model. See <http://releases.naturalcapitalproject.org/invest-userguide/latest/en/sdr.html> for additional explanations and image source.

Please refer to the guide available in <http://releases.naturalcapitalproject.org/invest-userguide/latest/en/sdr.html> for detailed information on the model characteristics and methodologies, including models data needs and outputs.

4.2.3. Seasonal Water Yield, data needs and model outputs

There is a growing demand for tools that can estimate the effect of landscape management on water supply services, such as irrigation, domestic consumption, and hydropower production. While the InVEST Annual Water Yield model provides an estimate of the total water yield for a catchment, many applications require knowledge of seasonal flows, particularly during the dry season. To achieve this, it is necessary to understand the hydrological processes that occur in a catchment, specifically the partitioning between quickflow (occurring during or shortly after rain events) and baseflow (occurring during dry weather). In highly seasonal climates, baseflow is likely to provide greater value than quickflow, unless significant storage (e.g. a large reservoir) is available. The InVEST Seasonal Water Yield model seeks to provide guidance on the contribution of land parcels to the generation of both baseflow and quickflow. The model calculates spatial indices that quantify the relative contribution of a parcel of land to the generation of both baseflow and quickflow. At present, there are no quantitative estimates of baseflow, only the relative contributions of pixels; a separate tool is in development to address this question.

Please refer to the guide available in http://releases.naturalcapitalproject.org/invest-userguide/latest/en/seasonal_water_yield.html for detailed information on the model characteristics and methodologies, including models data needs and outputs.

4.3. Crop production

Crop Production model allows users to estimate crop yields and the impacts of land use and management practices on crop production. The Crop Production model is based on a process-based approach that simulates the growth and development of crops over time, taking into account factors such as climate, soil properties, and management practices. The model includes a library of crop types that can be selected based on the user's specific needs and geographic region. It also provides estimates of crop yield, biomass production, and water use efficiency, which can be used to evaluate the effects of different management practices on crop production. The model also includes options for simulating the effects of climate change on crop yields. Additionally, the Crop Production model can be used to evaluate the impacts of land use change on crop production.

The Crop Production model requires input data such as climate data, soil properties and management practices. The model also requires information about the specific crop being modelled, such as planting date, planting density, and cultivar.

Overall, the Crop Production model in InVEST is a valuable tool for assessing the impacts of land use and management practices on crop production. The model provides estimates of crop yield, biomass production, and water use efficiency, and can be used to evaluate the effects of different management practices on crop production. The model is based on a process-based approach that simulates the growth and development of crops over time, and requires input data such as climate data, soil properties, and management practices.

For details about model use, methods, data needs and outputs, please refer to: http://releases.naturalcapitalproject.org/invest-userguide/latest/en/crop_production.html.

4.4. Biodiversity (Habitat quality)

The Habitat Quality model combines information on land use and cover (LULC) and biodiversity threats to produce habitat quality maps. This approach provides two important pieces of information useful for an initial assessment of conservation needs: the relative extent and degradation of different habitat types in a region, and changes over time. This approach also allows for a rapid assessment of habitat status and change as a proxy for more detailed measures of biodiversity status. When habitat changes are considered representative of genetic, species or ecosystem changes, the user assumes that areas with high quality habitats better support all levels of biodiversity and that a decline in the extent and quality of habitats over time represents a decline in the persistence, resilience, breadth and depth of biodiversity in the area where the decline is occurring.

The habitat rarity part of the model shows the extent and pattern of natural land cover types in the current or potential future landscape compared to the extent of the same natural land cover types in a given baseline period. Rarity maps allow the user to create a map of the rarest habitats in the landscape compared to the user-selected baseline to show the mix of habitats in the landscape that is most suitable for the native biodiversity of the study area.

The model requires baseline data available virtually anywhere in the world and is therefore useful in areas where little or no species distribution data is available. Comprehensive occurrence (presence/absence) data may be available in many locations for current conditions. However, modelling changes in occurrence, persistence or threats to multiple species under future conditions is often impossible or infeasible. A habitat approach ignores the detailed species occurrence data available for current conditions, but several of its components represent a functional advance over many existing biodiversity conservation planning tools. Most important is the ability to characterise the sensitivity of habitat types to different threats. Not all habitats are affected by all threats in the same way, and the

model accounts for this variability. In addition, the model can be used to estimate the relative impact of one threat compared to another, so that threats that are more damaging to the persistence of biodiversity in the landscape can be represented as such. For example, grasslands might be particularly sensitive to threats from urban areas, while only moderately sensitive to threats from roads. In addition, the distance over which a threat affects natural systems is included in the model.

The model assessment of the current landscape can be used as input for a rough assessment of current conservation needs and opportunities. The model assessment of the potential LULC future can be used to measure potential changes in the extent, quality and rarity of habitats in a landscape, as well as future conservation needs and opportunities.

Please refer to the guide available in http://releases.naturalcapitalproject.org/invest-userguide/latest/en/habitat_quality.html for detailed information on the model characteristics and methodologies, including models' data needs and outputs.

4.5. Biodiversity (Pollination abundance)

A wide range of animals can be important pollinators, but bees are the most important group for most crops. The InVEST Pollination model focuses on the resource needs and flight behaviours of wild bees. Wild bees also contribute to crop pollination and for several important crops, native species are more efficient and effective pollinators than honeybees. This is the pollination service associated with habitat conservation. For bees to persist on a landscape, they need two things: suitable places to nest, and sufficient food (provided by flowers) near their nesting sites. The Pollination model translates land cover into an index of suitability for bees to create a pollinator source map. This model incorporates the potential use of managed bees into a yield index. With information on the location of crops and their dependence on pollinators, the model uses a simple yield function to project how wild pollinator abundance in agricultural areas and the use of managed bees contributes to an index of crop yields.

Please refer to the guide available in <http://releases.naturalcapitalproject.org/invest-userguide/latest/en/croppollination.html> for detailed information on the model characteristics and methodologies, including models' data needs and outputs.

4.6. Cultural services (Recreation value).

The purpose of the recreation model is to predict the spread of person-days of recreation and tourism, based on the locations of natural habitats, accessibility, and built features that factor into people's decisions about where to recreate. The tool outputs maps showing current patterns of recreational use and, optionally, maps of future use under alternative scenarios. This model is based on the travel cost method, which estimates the value of recreational activities based on the time and money people spend to participate in them.

The recreation model includes several key components, including recreational resources, recreational facilities, and recreational activities. These components are evaluated using a variety of indicators, such as the frequency of visits to natural areas, travel costs and willingness to pay for recreational activities. The recreation model is used to estimate the overall efficiency of recreational use by taking into account the efficiency of each selected component.

The recreation model is an important tool for estimating the value of recreational services provided by natural resources, which can be used to inform policy and management decisions related to sustainable development and environmental safety.

Please refer to the guide available in <http://releases.naturalcapitalproject.org/invest-userguide/latest/en/recreation.html> for detailed information on the model characteristics and methodologies, including models' data needs and outputs.

5. Other options for ecosystem service assessment in the UNDERTREES: INCA project solutions.

The aforementioned set of models, based on the concepts and methods developed by the Natural Capital project, are conceived as enough to cover the essential ecosystem services potentially assessed under the framework of the UNDETREES project. Nevertheless, since InVEST models' data requirements could be difficult to be fulfilled for some services or in particular areas, and considering the premise that ecosystem service assessment approach in the UNDERTREES requires flexibility to facilitate implementation and adaptation to the local needs, alternative methodological approaches are suggested, particularly for those cases where ecosystem services are considered relevant and there is a lack of data.

The European Integrated Natural Capital Accounting (INCA) project ([About INCA | INCA Platform \(europa.eu\)](#)) consist on a European Union initiative that aims to develop a standardized framework for natural capital accounting (Figure 9). The INCA project collects and analyses a range of data related to natural resources and ecosystem services. Here are some specific types of data that are collected and analysed:

- Satellite imagery: The INCA project uses satellite imagery to monitor changes in land use and land cover, as well as to identify areas of high biodiversity or ecosystem services value.
- Land use data: The project also incorporates data on land use, which can help to identify areas where natural capital is being degraded or where ecosystem services are at risk.
- Statistical data: Statistical data on economic activity and ecosystem services are used to assess the value of natural resources and ecosystem services.
- Valuation techniques: The project incorporates a range of valuation techniques, such as market-based valuation, cost-based valuation and benefit transfer, to assess the economic value of natural resources and ecosystem services.
- Ecosystem services data: The INCA project aims to develop a standardized classification system for ecosystem services, which can help decision-makers understand the benefits that ecosystems provide.
- Soil erosion and sediment transport data: The InVEST Sediment Delivery Ratio (SDR) module is a tool used to model soil erosion and sediment transport and deposition phenomena.
- Carbon storage data: The InVEST Carbon Storage and Sequestration model is used to assess the impacts of urbanization on carbon storage variation.

The project provides already prepared data and maps of provisioning, regulating/maintenance and cultural ecosystem services for a number of years. The set of ecosystem services covered are: Crop provision, wood provision, carbon sequestration, Crop pollination, flood control, habitat and species maintenance, water purification and nature-based recreation.

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